

Organizational Culture, Leadership Styles Influence on Performance through Motivation as a Mediation Variables

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Abstract: This study aims to examine and analyze the influence of organizational culture and leadership style on employee performance through motivation as a mediating variable. Respondents were 71 employees. The analytical tool used is path analysis. The results showed that organizational culture, leadership style, and motivation influence the performance of employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah East Java Tbk Malang Branch, both partially and simultaneously. While motivation does not play a role as a mediating variable on the influence of organizational culture and leadership style on performance. Strong organizational culture and the application of appropriate leadership styles, have an influence on employee performance. This is an important consideration for management, so they can get a strategic picture of future performance improvements

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Leadership Style, Performance, and Motivation

I. INTRODUCTION

Competition in the financial services business, both in terms of products and promotions offered by various financial institutions, is constantly increasing. The attractiveness of the financial services business is quite large and promising. This can be seen from the number of financial institutions, both banks and non-banks that are engaged in this business. Therefore, it becomes a challenge for a financial service provider to provide the best performance in providing services. PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk, one of the Regional Development Banks in Indonesia was established on August 17, 1961 in Surabaya, has a vision to become the number 1 (one) Regional Development Bank. PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk is headquartered in Surabaya, has 41 (forty one) conventional branch offices and 7 (seven) sharia branch offices spread across the provinces of East Java, DKI Jakarta and Batam.

PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch Office which is located at Jalan Jaksa Agung Suprpto No.26-28 Malang City is one of the largest branch offices in East Java. Given its strategic location, of course Bank Jatim also has many competitors in the business of providing financial services. Therefore, employees are required to be able to show their best performance in providing services. In addition, technological advances and the demands of customer needs are also factors that are considered in presenting the best performance.

The next leader has a leadership style that leads to authoritarianism and seems oriented to image only. The leader also does not have warm communication with his subordinates. However, it is different from the next leadership, where this leader is classified as a friendly and communicative person. During his time as a leader, he puts forward responsibility and teamwork. So it can be concluded that the existence of a leader with their respective leadership styles has had a different impact on employee performance. Further information was obtained that, it is not uncommon for a change of leadership to have an unpleasant impact on most employees. Changes that are considered drastic sometimes actually lead to decreased employee morale. However, it is not uncommon for there to be leaders who are able to embrace subordinates, thus creating synergy in achieving company goals. This is inseparable from how each leader manages his subordinates.

Until now, the organizational culture that has developed in the work environment of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch Office is in the form of a passion to provide the best service to customers, exceeding expected expectations. In addition, cooperation between lines is also put forward in order to achieve company goals. One of the cultures that has been implemented to date is the routine briefings that all employees carry out before providing services to customers. However, the implementation of briefings which tended to be monotonous, took a long

time, and just became a routine was felt to have a negative impact in the form of boredom and ineffectiveness for employees. At the time of the initial research survey, PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch Office had leaders who prioritizes communication with employees, prioritizes a culture of cooperation, and is willing to listen to employee complaints and provide solutions to difficulties raised by employees.

Given the target of Bank Jatim in general, which wants to establish itself as the best bank on a national scale, however, the enthusiasm of employees to be able to gain customer sympathy, especially savings customers is still considered lacking. Supposedly, the achievement of third party funds achieved by PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch Office is able to compete with other banks. However, the current situation shows that employees do not have sufficient motivation to achieve these goals. Performance is a fundamental foundation for achieving the goals of an organization. The success of an organization in improving its performance greatly depends on the quality of the human resources involved in working while in the organization. Furthermore, the role of human resources in organizational performance is very important, human resource decisions must be able to increase efficiency and even be able to provide an increase in organizational results and also have an impact on increasing community satisfaction (Logahan, 2016).

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Meanwhile, Wahyuni (2015) entitled *The Influence of Organizational Culture and Leadership Style on Employee Performance in Public Sector Organizations with Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable (Case Study on Tasikmalaya City Government Employees)*, states that Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through positive Work Motivation with influence mediation and there is a positive influence of leadership style on employee performance through work motivation. Kharis's (2015) research entitled *The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Employee Performance with Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable (A Study on Employees of Bank Jatim, Malang Branch)*, states that transformational leadership style has an effect on the performance of transformational leadership style has an indirect effect on employee performance through work motivation. Research with the title *The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Physical Work Environment on Employee Performance with Work Motivation as a Mediating Variable (Study on Regional Drinking Water Companies (PDAM), Kendari City)* conducted by Bana (2016) states that transformational leadership and physical work environments have an influence. positive and significant directly on employee performance, transformational leadership.

Research by Amalia, et.al (2016) with the title *Influence of Leadership Style on Work Motivation and Employee Performance (Study of Employees of Kebon Agung Sugar Factory Malang)*, obtained results that transactional leadership style has a significant effect on work motivation, transformational leadership style has no significant effect on

work motivation, transactional leadership style has a significant effect on employee performance, transformational leadership style has no significant effect on employee performance, work motivation has a significant effect on employee performance, work motivation mediates transactional leadership style on employee performance, work motivation mediates transformational leadership style on employee performance. Isnaini (2016) with the research title *The Effect of Leadership Style and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Work Motivation* (Studies at the Regional Education and Training Agency Office of Jambi province) states that leadership style and organizational culture have a significant positive influence on motivation, leadership style and organizational culture through motivation to have significant influence on performance.

Josephine and Dhyah (2017) with the research title *The Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance in the Production Section through Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable at PT. Trio Corporate Plastics (Tricopla)*, got the results of the Work Environment influencing Work Motivation and Employee Performance; Work motivation affects employee performance; and Work Motivation is proven as an intervening variable between the influence of the Work Environment on Employee Performance. Hanafi (2017) with the title *Influence of Motivation, and Work Environment, on Employee Performance, With Job Satisfaction as a Mediation Variable At PT BNI Lifeinsurance*, the results show that motivation on employee performance has a positive and significant effect, which means that motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Motivation for employee performance mediated by job satisfaction also has a significant effect, positive job satisfaction mediates the relationship between work environment and employee performance.

Emil and Albertis (2019) with the title *The Influence of Leadership Style, Organizational Culture, and Work Environment on Employee Performance through Motivation at PDAM Tirta Mayang Jambi City*, stated that leadership style, organizational culture and motivation have a positive and significant effect on performance, and the work environment has an effect. negative and insignificant influence on employee performance. In addition to organizational culture and leadership style, motivational factors can also affect employee performance. Someone is not necessarily willing to give all their abilities to achieve optimal results, so there is a need for a motivation so that they want to use their full potential. This driving force is called motivation. Leaders must always provide direction, foster, and motivate subordinates in completing work to achieve organizational goals. This is always done by the leadership by providing motivation and a balance of wages for the work of employees (Moehriono, 2012). This study raises the problems that occur at PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch, especially regarding the influence of organizational culture and leadership style as well as the role of motivation as a mediation on the formation of employee performance.

The results of the study using a number of variables that have an influence on the formation of performance become an attraction for researchers to find out more about other factors that determine the formation of performance. The choice of the location of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch was motivated by the existence of researchers as employees who had been assigned to that place. So it is expected that it will be easier to obtain access to information. In addition, the target of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch to achieve achievement as BPD number one in the national ranking requires information about things that can improve the performance of its employees. So that the results of this study are expected to provide this information. In addition, according to the results of the initial survey by conducting a series of interviews with employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch, information was obtained about problems related to the formation of employee performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational culture

Organizational culture is a basic thought pattern that is taught to new personnel as a way to feel, think, and act right from day to day, Luthans (2006). Meanwhile, Moehriono (2012) defines organizational culture as a pattern of organizational beliefs and values that are understood, imbued, and practiced by the organization so that this pattern gives its own meaning and becomes the basis for the rules of behavior in the organization.

According to Robbins (2003) the notion of organizational culture is a system of shared meanings adopted by members that differentiates an organization from other organizations. This system of shared meaning, when observed more closely, is a set of key characteristics valued by an organization. A strong and healthy organizational culture is an issue that has been described by many companies at the global level. Robbins, (2002) states that a strong culture will have a big influence on the behavior of its members because the high level of togetherness and intensity creates an internal climate of high behavioral control. In a strong culture, the core values of the organization are upheld and upheld together. The more members who accept the core values and the greater their commitment to those values, the stronger

the culture. Thus a strong culture will have a big influence on the behavior of its members because high levels of togetherness and intensity create an internal atmosphere in the form of high behavioral control (Robbins, 2002). Likewise, on the contrary, a weak culture in an organization will create a climate that is less conducive. Employee work behavior in organization is not only determined by one factor, but also influenced by several factors. These factors can come from the employee's personal self or from outside factors (Gibson, 1996). The results of the interaction between these two variables in the organization form a culture that not only affects employee work behavior, but also affects their performance. If the culture that is built between individuals and their environment is not strong enough, it will certainly bring an impact on the weak awareness of organizational members to achieve organizational goals. Tika (2006) states that organizational culture helps performance because it creates an extraordinary level of motivation for employees. This is in line with the opinion (Yudhaningsih, 2011) which states that organizational culture has the aim of changing the attitudes and behavior of existing human resources in order to increase work productivity to face various challenges in the future.

Leadership Style Theory

According to Tjiptono (2006) leadership style is a way that leaders interact with their subordinates. Leadership style is the way managers behave and carry out their authority. This style may be autocratic or democratic, hard or soft, formal or informal. The style used by managers will be influenced by the culture and values of the company. This style does not depend on the level of individual behavior but will also be influenced by the leadership situation in which people are placed (Armstrong in Atto'illah, 2014). Meanwhile, according to Hersey (2004) which means that leadership style is a pattern of behavior (words and actions) that are felt by others. Leadership style is a behavior norm that is used by someone when trying to influence the behavior of others or subordinates. Leaders who are effective in applying a certain style of leadership must first understand who the subordinates they lead are, understand the strengths and weaknesses of their subordinates, and understand how to use the strengths of their subordinates to compensate for their weaknesses.

Employee performance

According to Ainsworth (2014), performance is the end point of certain people, resources, and the environment that are gathered together with the intention of producing certain things, whether tangible products or services that are less visible directly. To the extent that these interactions yield results in the desired level and quality, at the agreed cost level performance will be judged satisfactory, good, or perhaps excellent. Conversely, if the results are disappointing, for whatever reason, the performance will be assessed as poor or deteriorate. This opinion emphasizes that the performance of an employee / employee is the result or output of a job assigned to an organization / institution (Fattah, 2014).

Motivation Theory

Motivation is a process that begins with a physiological or psychological deficiency that drives behaviors or drives aimed at incentive purposes. Thus, the key to understanding the motivation process depends on understanding and the relationship between needs, drives, and incentives (Luthans, 2006). Meanwhile, Sudarwan Danim (2004) states that work motivation is a precondition for an individual to behave in the work he is engaged in. High motivation tends to result in high achievement, and low motivation tends to produce low achievement, as well as in rewards. The effect of the award can be in the form of satisfaction or dissatisfaction which will provide feedback on the next work motivation. Another opinion states that work motivation can be defined as a psychological boost to someone who determines the direction of a person's behavior in an organization, the level of effort and the level of persistence or resilience in facing an obstacle or problem (level of persistence). So work motivation can be interpreted as the morale that exists in employees that enables these employees to work to achieve certain goals (George and Jones, 2005 in Tania and Sutanto, 2013).

While work motivation according to J. Winardi (2001) in Herisman (2006) is a potential power that exists within a human being that can be developed by himself or developed by outside forces which essentially revolve around monetary and non-monetary rewards that can affect the results of his performance positive or negative, it depends on the situation and conditions faced by the person concerned. The basic theory is the basis for understanding the explanation of motivation, in his book Siagian (2009), the theory according to Abraham H. Maslow argues that there are internal needs that greatly affect human motivation at work.

III. METHOD

Types of research

This research is a type of quantitative research. In terms of the level of explanation, this research is an associative study with a form of causal relationship. Sugiyono (2013) a causal relationship is a relationship that is causal in nature. This

means that the research focuses on organizational culture, leadership style, and work environment as independent variables, employee performance as the dependent variable, and motivation as a mediating variable.

Population and Sample

The population in this study were 240 employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch Offices, including outsourced and permanent employees. The sample technique used in this study was purposive sampling method, namely the sampling technique of a population that has a consideration For certain characteristics, using the Slovin formula, the number of samples in this study was 72 people.

IV. Data Analysis Method

In this study, data analysis using path analysis (path analysis). This technique is used to test the amount of contribution (contribution) shown by the path coefficient on each path diagram of the causal relationship between variables X1 X2 and X3 to Y2 and its impact on Y1.

V. RESULT

Path Analysis

The calculation phase begins by performing Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. The variables of organizational culture and leadership style on motivation are presented as follows:

Table 1. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results Influence of Organizational Culture Variables (X1) and Leadership Style (X2), on Motivation (Y1)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	12.201	1.701		7.174	.000
	Budaya Organisasi	.202	.081	.308	2.483	.015
	Gaya Kepemimpinan	.214	.076	.351	2.827	.006

a. Dependent Variable: Motivasi

Followed by performing Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. Organizational culture variables, leadership style, which are presented in Table 2 as follows:

Table 2. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of the Influence of Organizational Culture (X1), Leadership Style (X2), and Motivation (Y1) Variables on Performance (Y2)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.355	2.246		2.830	.006
	Budaya Organisasi	.222	.084	.307	2.629	.011
	Gaya Kepemimpinan	.180	.080	.266	2.252	.028
	Motivasi	.277	.121	.250	2.289	.025

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Table 3 Calculation of Path Analysis as follows:

Table 3. Summary of Path Analysis Calculations

No	Test result	Coefficient	Annova	Model Summary
1.	X1 and X2 influence Y1	X ₁ =0,308 X ₂ =0,351	18,473	0,352
2.	X1, X2, and Y1 influence Y2	X ₁ =0,307 X ₂ =0,266 Y ₁ =0,250	20,756	0,482

So that the summary diagram of the calculation of the equation can be drawn as follows:

The conclusion of the direct effect on the indirect effect is presented in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4. Summary of the Calculation Results of the Influence of Variable Organizational Culture (X1), Leadership Style (X2) through Motivation (Y1)

No	Independent Variable	Dependent variable	Dependent variable	Indirect Influence	Conclusion
1.	X ₁	Y ₁	0,308		
2.	X ₂		0,351		
3.	X ₁	Y ₂	0,307		
4.	X ₂		0,266		
5.	Y ₁		0,250		
6.	X ₁ □ Y ₂	Y ₁		0,077	Direct effect □ indirect effect □ mediation is not effective
7.	X ₂ □ Y ₂			0,088	Direct effect □ indirect effect □ mediation is not effective

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section will present a discussion of the results of the analysis that has been carried out on the influence of organizational culture and leadership style on performance mediated by motivation at PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch. The explanation is as follows:

The influence of organizational culture and leadership style on motivation of employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch Office either partially or simultaneously

The results of the tests that have been done state that the tcount of Organizational Culture (X1) is 2.483, which is greater than the 1.990 level and the significance level of 0.015 is smaller than the 0.05 significance level, so it can be concluded that the organizational culture variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on motivation. (Y1). So it can be concluded that organizational culture partially influences the motivation of the employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch. The results of this study are also supported by research conducted by Isnaini (2016), Emil and Albertis (2019), where it is stated that a strong organizational culture has an influence on employee motivation. The more members who accept the core values and the greater their commitment to those values, the stronger the culture. A strong organizational culture will have a big influence on the behavior of its members because

high levels of togetherness and intensity create an internal atmosphere in the form of high behavioral control (Robbins and Judge, 2008).

The tcount of Leadership Style (X2) is 2.827, which is greater than t table of 1.990 and the significance level of 0.006 is smaller than the significance level of 0.05, so it can be concluded that the variable Leadership Style (X2) has a positive and significant effect on motivation (Y1). So it can be concluded that the leadership style partially influences the motivation of the employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch. This result is supported by research conducted by Wahyuni and Kharis (2015), which states that the implementation of the right leadership style for employees will support the birth of work motivation. This is also supported by the results of filling out a questionnaire where the items of leadership style that are presented show an influence on the formation of motivation in employees. The result of the Fcount value test is 18.437 with sig. 0.000 and the value of Ftable 2.70, it can be stated that the value of Fcount is greater than Ftable, so it can be concluded that organizational culture and leadership style simultaneously affect the motivation of employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch.

The influence of organizational culture, leadership style, and motivation on the performance of the employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch Office either partially or simultaneously.

The results of the tests carried out stated that the tcount of Organizational Culture (X1) was 2.629, which was greater than ttable 2,000 and the significance level of 0.011 was smaller than the 0.05 significance level, so it can be concluded that the organizational culture variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on performance (Y2). So it can be concluded that organizational culture partially influences the performance of the employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch. These results are in line with research with the results obtained by Wahyuni (2015), Isnaini (2016), and Emil and Albertis (2019), which suggest that organizational culture has a significant effect on performance. This is further strengthened by the opinion of Molenaar (2002), Kotter and Heskett in Koesmono (2005) which states that culture has full power, affects individuals and their performance. So it can be concluded that the higher the value of an organizational culture, the better the resulting performance will be.

The t value of Leadership Style (X2) is 2.252 greater than t table 2,000 and the significance level of 0.028 is smaller than the significance level of 0.05, so it can be concluded that the Leadership Style variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on performance (Y2). So it is concluded that the leadership style partially influences the performance of the employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch. These results are in line with research conducted by Rusady and Suprayitno (2011), Wahyuni (2015), and Isnaini (2016) which states that leadership style affects performance. This is confirmed by the opinion of Mangkunegara (2009) which states that performance is influenced by organizational factors including leadership style. So it can be stated that the better and more precise the leadership style is applied, the higher the employee's performance.

The t value of Motivation (X2) is 2.252, which is greater than t table of 2,000 and the significance level of 0.028 is smaller than the significance level of 0.05, so it can be concluded that the leadership style variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on performance (Y2). So it can be concluded that motivation partially influences the performance of the employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch. This result is also supported by the results of research conducted by Permanasari 2013 and Theodora (2015) which state that motivation has an influence on performance. Besides that, it is also confirmed by Davis's opinion in Mangkunegara (2009) which states that the factors that influence performance achievement are the ability and motivation factors. Therefore it can be concluded that the increase in motivation is in line with the increase in employee performance.

Based on the above test results, the Fcount value is 20.756 with sig. 0.000 and the value of Ftable 2.70, it can be stated that the value of Fcount is greater than Ftable, so it can be concluded that organizational culture, leadership style, and motivation together have an effect on the performance of the employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch.

The influence of organizational culture on performance mediated by motivation in employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch Office

Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out, the value of the direct influence of organizational culture variables on performance is 0.307, while the influence of organizational culture variables on performance through motivation is 0.077, so it is concluded that the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect, motivation does not play a role as a mediating variable in meditation. the influence of organizational culture on the performance of employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Wahyuni (2015), Lailatul (2016), Emil and Albetris (2019) which states that a strong organizational culture has an influence on the formation of performance in employees. Thus a strong culture will have a big influence on the

behavior of its members because high levels of togetherness and intensity create an internal atmosphere in the form of high behavioral control (Robbins and Judge, 2008). So that even without motivation, this strong organizational culture is enough to bring out the performance of the employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch.

Bank Jatim Organizational Culture in the form of excellence, professional, integrity, and innovation is an important foundation in forming good performance for employees. This is also proven by filling out a questionnaire where it is stated that the wide opportunities for innovation are able to optimize team performance, in which there are human resources who already have expertise in their respective fields. In addition, the accuracy and discipline that has been built has also proven to be able to make employees in a solid state in completing the targets given by the company. Besides that, the culture of working as a team but still upholding healthy competition is able to make employees remain professional in completing the tasks that are their responsibility.

The influence of leadership style on performance mediated by motivation on employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch Office

Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out, the value of the direct influence of the leadership style variable on performance is 0.266, while the influence of the leadership style variable on performance through motivation is 0.088, so it is concluded that the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect, motivation does not play a role as a mediating variable in meditation. the influence of leadership style on the performance of the employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Rusady and Suprayitno (2011), Amaliyah, et al. (2014), Wahyuni (2015), Amalia, et al. (2016), Isnaini (2016), and Emil and Albetris (2019) who state that the right leadership style can produce employee performance.

The effectiveness of the leader is influenced by the characteristics of his subordinates and is related to the communication process that occurs between the leader and subordinates. Kusumawati (2008) further explains that leader's behavior has a significant impact on employee attitudes, behavior and performance. So that without motivational encouragement, employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch have been able to achieve good performance in terms of performance.

This is also proven by filling out a questionnaire where it is stated that the right steps taken by the leader of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch are able to encourage people in the team to maximize performance according to their respective fields. The existence of a leader who is able to encourage the emergence of employee creativity helps the completion of predetermined targets. In addition, leadership behavior that reflects positive morals is also able to encourage employees to participate in exemplary ways, one of which is by applying discipline to work.

VII. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research that has been done, it can be explained further about the conclusions of the research results. The conclusions obtained are as follows: (1) Organizational culture and leadership style affect the performance of employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch (2) Organizational culture, leadership style, and motivation affect employee performance. A well-executed work culture and the leadership style of the nurturing Branch Leader can provide additional motivation for employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch in working so that they can achieve the targets set by company management (3) motivation does not play a role as mediating variables on the influence of organizational culture on the performance of employees of PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Malang Branch.

We recommend that PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Branch Malang has an organizational culture that has been formed in employees, so as to be able to maintain a positive culture to support the realization of performance. The right leadership style to be applied to employees, so as to bring the organization to achieve goals effectively and efficiently. Reference on the factors that influence the formation of performance, so as to get a strategic picture of future performance improvements.

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